

BORROWED WORDS IN THE UZBEK LANGUAGE

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Annotation: The Persian-Tajik language, Arabic language, Russian language, with which the Uzbek language interacted and was influenced, left a significant mark in the vocabulary of the Uzbek language. There are reasons for this. One of the most important reasons is the emergence of bilingualism in the life of the Uzbek people as a result of the contact of the Uzbek language with Persian-Tajik, Arabic and Russian languages. The interaction and cooperation of languages often leads to the exchange of words between these languages, the transfer of words from one language to another. Conditions are necessary for the transfer of words from one language to another.

Key words: Persian-Tajik language, bilingualism, neologisms, lexical meaning, borrowed words.

A loanword is a word that has been transferred from one language to another. For example, andisha, barg, tilla, shabnam, which have been adopted into the Uzbek language from the Persian-Tajik language; Arabic literature, ethics, book, teacher; the words bank, newspaper, samovar, television, etc., which were acquired from and through the Russian language. Borrowed words change from one language to another due to certain socio-historical events, trade and cultural contacts. In particular, due to the fact that the Uzbek people have been living side by side with the Tajiks for a long time under the same economic system, Persian-Tajik words, Arabic words as a result of the Arab invasion, Central Asia's approach to Russia Russian and European words entered the Uzbek language as a result of assimilation. Although the adopted word is in the nature of a neologism in the early period, it gradually obeys the laws of the receiving language, becomes natural and clear like its own word (leaf), phonetic reformation (bed), due to its grammatical assimilation (from the bank), its active participation in the word formation system (tractor), and its repeated use, its foreign element is not noticeable.

During its many centuries of historical development, the Uzbek language enriched and improved its vocabulary at the expense of its internal sources. According to this law, new words were created on the basis of their layers, the meanings of existing words were expanded, additional tasks were assigned to some words, the literary language was added to the literary language in folk dialects in different periods, according to the need, the words were accepted.

The possibilities of internal sources are an important basis for the enrichment of the vocabulary of the Uzbek language. However, just as no language in the world can rely on its own internal resources, the Uzbek language is not only dependent on its own words, its wealth and capabilities. External sources play an important role in enriching and improving the vocabulary of the Uzbek language. In general, any language cannot live in a pure state. It is legal for different languages to have certain relations with each other in different historical conditions. Such an attitude can leave certain traces in the development of the languages in contact, especially in its vocabulary. For this reason, two laws are observed that are common to changes in the vocabulary of all languages in the world, including the vocabulary of the Uzbek language:

- 1) replace the old with the new;
- 2) receiving words from other languages.

So, the vocabulary of the Uzbek language relies on two sources in its development:

- a) internal source;
- b) external source.

So, the words in the lexicon of the Uzbek language are not genetically related only to the lexicon of the ancient Turkic tribal languages (common Turkic words). In addition to the words of its own layer, it also contains words adopted from other languages in different periods. The influence of other languages on the Uzbek language can be seen in two important cases:

1. Accepting words from a foreign language into the Uzbek language.
2. Adapting foreign language words to the Uzbek language.

The entry and assimilation of words from one language to another is not just a simple process, but a law related to complex linguistic and socio-historical conditions. In order for words to be learned from one language to another, there must first be real conditions. Such conditions are mutual cooperation of languages, that is, communication between languages. The current Uzbek language has historically experienced complex stages of development and formation. The Uzbek language was in contact with a number of sister languages, as well as foreign languages, during the periods of clan and tribal language, folk language, national language, and the language of the social nation. The language of Turkic clans and tribes has been in contact with Iranian languages that have lived in Central Asia since ancient times. The people who lived in Central Asia, including in the territory of present-day Uzbekistan, spoke local language dialects belonging to the Iranian language group. This was the language of the

Iranian clan - tribes, peoples - Sogds, Sakas, Massagets, Bactrians, Parthians, Parikanians, Khorezmians and others.

Also, in the ancient Kingdom of Bactria, Greek was used, as well as a language consisting of a mixture of Greek and Iranian languages. The ancient Khorezm language, which had the characteristics of an Iranian language, existed in Central Asia, including present-day Uzbekistan. There was a known connection between this language and the local Turkic languages of that time. There are evidences in historical sources that show that Khorezm writing was widespread in the VII-VIII centuries and before. It is known that in the 13th and 14th centuries, the inhabitants of Khorezm spoke two languages - Turkish and the ancient language of Khorezm. The ancient Khorezm language was assimilated into the Uzbek language by the 14th century. As a result, some words related to this language have been preserved in modern Uzbek: хоп (хоб), bog, pochcha (picchomi-dadam), sky (osm), juft (er), ariq (ar -water) and others. In the past, the Uzbek language has been in contact with a number of unrelated languages and languages from other systems. Such languages are Persian-Tajik and Arabic. Also, the Uzbek language entered the period of its development as a national language and the language of the social nation and entered into communication and cooperation with the Russian language, and this process continues. The connection of the Uzbek language with foreign languages has different levels and qualitative manifestations. Some languages with which the Uzbek language is in contact have not left a significant mark in the lexicon of the Uzbek language. In particular, only a few words from Indian and ancient Greek languages entered the Uzbek language.

Some words belonging to Indian, Greek, Latin, Chinese, Mongolian languages are also found in the works of Alisher Navoi. The Persian-Tajik language, Arabic language, Russian language, with which the Uzbek language interacted and was influenced, left a significant mark in the vocabulary of the Uzbek language. There are reasons for this. One of the most important reasons is the emergence of bilingualism in the life of the Uzbek people as a result of the contact of the Uzbek language with Persian-Tajik, Arabic and Russian languages. The interaction and cooperation of languages often leads to the exchange of words between these languages, the transfer of words from one language to another. Conditions are necessary for the transfer of words from one language to another. This condition is not just a connection of two languages, living side by side, territorial convergence, but mutual influence, cooperation, and the phenomenon of bilingualism arising on this basis. In history, the Uzbek language

has been in contact with sister languages belonging to the Turkic language family, such as Kazakh, Kyrgyz, Uyghur, Karakalpak, Uyghur, Turkmen, and Azerbaijani languages. This relationship continues even now.

Thanks to this connection, in many regions of Uzbekistan, people who can speak Uzbek and Kyrgyz, Uzbek and Kazakh, Turkmen and Uzbek, Tatar and Uzbek, Karakalpak and Uzbek in parallel there is a bilingual population. The ability to speak two genetically related languages has been present among the people living in Uzbekistan since ancient times. The development of international relations, international economic, political, cultural relations and their effects are reflected in the lexicon of the languages of these nations. There are countless studies devoted to the importance and role of such phenomena. But, despite this, the debates and discussions in this regard have not ended. Because linguists have not come to a common and firm conclusion on the issue of word acquisition.

For almost 300 years, linguists of the world have been studying a number of issues such as determining the laws of language interaction, studying the reasons and characteristics of foreign words assimilation, determining their roles and tasks in the languages that have been assimilated. The combination of more or less adopted words and phrases in almost all the developed languages of the world, and even the mixed features of some languages, attract the attention of linguists first of all, and everyone who pays attention to language. In particular, objective factors such as the fact that foreign words quickly obey the laws of the host language, and become adapted to the native language without knowing that it is foreign, have turned the issue of word acquisition into one of the most urgent problems of linguistics. The number of foreign words in the Uzbek language is slightly more than 40 percent, of which slightly more than 26 percent belong to the Russian language. In general, the amount of borrowed words in the Uzbek language does not make a significant contribution. Because almost 60 percent of Russian and European languages have adopted words. Moreover, not all of the words whose names have been acquired have been acquired from abroad. Transferring words from one language to another is a positive thing.

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